

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

БИОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ КОНЦЕПЦИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННЫЙ ПЕРИОД, ТЕОРИЯ И ЗАКОНЫ УЧЕБНАЯ СИТУАЦИЯ

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BIOLOGICAL CONCEPT IN MODERN PERIOD, THEORY AND LAWS TEACHING SITUATION

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Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются перспективы развития биологического образования, стоящие перед ним задачи подготовки кадров в соответствии с мировыми стандартами в современное время и возможности решения проблемы. В статье также рассматривается состояние преподавания биологических понятий, теорий и законов в высшей и средней школе.

Abstract

The article discusses the prospects for the development of biological education, the tasks ahead for the training of human resources in accordance with world standards in modern times, and opportunities to solve the problem. The article also discusses the state of teaching biological concepts, theories and laws in higher and secondary schools. The impact of the correct use of integration and differentiation in the teaching of biological knowledge, concepts, theories and laws on the comprehensive and in-depth acquisition of biological knowledge was also noted.

Ключевые слова: биологическая концепция, теория, закон, интеграция, обучение.

Keywords: biological concept, theory, law, integration, educating.

According to the "Theory of the Development of Concepts", knowledge consists of concepts defined by science of objects and events, signs and properties of processes, and their existing interactions. By understanding the external world, a person feels, perceives, imagines and finally generalizes objects and events, their signs with the senses: *Man - feeling - perception - imagination - understanding - judgement - generalization*. So, the concept is a generalized idea (9, p.63). Contrary to the widely spread opinion among people, the word "theory" does not actually mean "unconfirmed or unfounded thought" in science. In science, "law", "rule" is an observation of a natural fact, a phenomenon. In the teaching of biology, biological concepts form the basis of the learning process. As a result, the three main functions of instruction are: *teaching, educating and developing* (8, p. 62). The correct use of integration and differentiation in the teaching of biological knowledge, concepts, theories and laws will create conditions for the comprehensive and in-depth mastery of biological knowledge (3). The integration of learning serves to create an unbreakable connection between different knowledge systems (biological, chemical, physical systems, etc.), to form a complete picture of nature in general, and the differentiation of learning serves to deepen knowledge in a definite and specific area according to students' interests (7, p. 35).

The introduction of new pedagogical and educational technologies in our education does not harm the legacy of pedagogy, but rather develops it. For this reason, in recent years, the integration of

technology in education has played a special role in increasing visibility, especially in the teaching of biology (3, p. 5). The transfer of concepts to skills is possible in all biology courses. The development of skills is related to the development of concepts. In order to develop knowledge, skills and habits, it is important to first develop their content. First simple skills should be formed, and then more perfect and complex skills (1, p. 149). At present, due to curriculum reforms in the field of education, qualitative changes are being made in the teaching process. The subject-oriented curriculum in terms of content is aimed at mastering these concepts, covering the field of science and its system of perfect concepts. The purpose of the implementation of all practical skills is to serve to increase the strength and sustainability of knowledge (10, p. 5).

21st century education is radically different from traditional teaching in terms of teaching process, methods, techniques and tools. With the emergence of activities in different formats between teachers and learners, it has become necessary to organize the management of education in higher and secondary schools in accordance with the problems of the time. Today, we cannot be satisfied with students who memorize various scientific knowledge. Learners need to be taken out of the "folder" format where knowledge is stored. Teaching can be considered effective when the young generation, who are able to apply knowledge creatively, are critical of the proposed ready-made knowledge, and think constructively, apply what they have learned (4, 5, 6, 11).

The teaching of biological concepts, theories and laws requires a special approach in modern times. In order to increase the efficiency of the teaching process, it is no longer enough to ask questions in class, listen to lessons and solve homework. As biology is an experimental science, the existing opportunities and tools must be used to turn biological knowledge into practical skills and abilities into habits. But what opportunities should be used? And how? *That is: What to teach? How to teach? How to organize? How to evaluate?* (8, p.5). Failure to solve these issues reduces the quality of education. There are many reasons why

biological concepts are not well understood and remembered. The basics are as follows: a) learners' knowledge remains in the form of perception and imagination; b) lack of systematic development of concepts; c) not related to other concepts, etc. Improving the quality of thoughtful activity depends on the level of questions asked. For example: What is the difference between the structure and function of a leaf's skin? What is the difference between the leaves of light-loving and shade-tolerant plants? How are seeds different from spores? The role of diagrams and tables in the teaching of concepts is great (8, pp. 70, 71):

Nucleic acid name	Chemical composition	Molecular structure	State in the cell	Functions
DNA	Carbohydrate			
RNA	Nitrogenous base			

Repetition of concepts is less repeated in the course of plants, and in the course of animals in almost all subjects. The most important concepts in a general biology course must be developed in a logical sequence. For example, the topic of development of the organic world should be linked to the reproduction and individual development of the organism with elementary evolution concepts of plants and animals in grades VII-VIII, elemental cell division in grade IX, and the

“Concept of soil”, plant groups in grade VI. A teacher who clearly understands the theory of concept development, chooses the right materials and methods for the lesson, uses the methods of methodological approach on the spot. All questions are problem-solving, systematic, and use visual aids effectively (9).

There are about 20 theories and rules in the literature, the identified laws and theories are shown in the following table:

Table 1.

Laws used in teaching biology

In high school	In secondary school
1. V.N. Vernadsky's law of biogenic migration of atoms 2. N.I. Vavilov's law of homologous series of hereditary variability 3. Mendel's law of identity of first generation hybrids 4. Mendel's law of fragmentation of second generation (F2) hybrids 5. G. Mendel's law of free distribution of genes 6. Natural-historical law 7. K.M. Ber's law of similarity of embryos 8. A.O. Kovalevsky's law of reduction and simplification of the limbs in the process of evolution 9. Cuvier's law of correlation of parts of organisms or ratio of organs 10. L. Dollo's law of irreversibility of evolution 11. The law of the same direction of energy flow, etc.	1. "Biogenetic" law of F. Müller and E. Haeckel 2. Mendel's law of fragmentation of second generation (F2) hybrids 3. Mendel's law of free distribution of genes 4. Morgan's law of attachment of genes located on the same chromosome 5. N.I. Vavilov's law of homologous series of hereditary variability 6. Hardy-Weinberg's law of stability of the relative frequency of genes during free crossing in generations

In addition to the laws used in the teaching of biology, it is important to have an in-depth interpretation of the theories and hypotheses taught in biology.

Table 2.

In high school	In secondary school
1. T. Schwan's "Cell" theory	T. Schwan's "Cell" theory
2. The theory of evolution	The theory of evolution
3. Darwin's theory of divergence	Divergence is mentioned in secondary school
4. Chromosome theory of heredity	
5. The balance theory of sex	It was taught before
6. The theory of physiological determination of sex	
7. T.D. Lysenko's theory of gradual development	
8. N.I. Vavilov's theory of important centers of origin of cultivated plants in the world	It is taught, but not considered a theory
9. A. Forman's fibrillar network theory of protoplasm	
10. R. Altman's granular theory of protoplasm	
11. Wilson's colloid theory of protoplasm	Basically the content is taught, not considered a theory
12. Defusion mutation theory	
13. A.N. Bach's theory of peroxide, etc.	

The table shows that insufficient attention is paid to the teaching of biological laws and theories in secondary schools. Research shows that 6 out of 27 laws taught in higher education schools, and only 5 out of 22 theories and hypotheses are mentioned or partially reported. It has been established that not all existing biological laws can be applied to secondary school

courses. However, there are laws that are important to bring to secondary school. For example, Mendel's law of identity of first generation hybrids (7, 116-117;). According to professor A.M. Huseynov, in order to more effectively organize the teaching of biology, it was important to bring 9 biological laws to secondary school courses:

Table 3.

Laws required for teaching in high school

Topics	New laws to be brought to the course
Identity in the first generation of hybrids	G. Mendel's law of identity of first generation hybrids K.M. Berin's law of similarity of embryos
Embryological evidence (similarity of embryos)	
Phylogenetic sequences	A. O. Kovalevsky's law of reduction and simplification of the limbs in the process of evolution L. Dollo's law of irreversibility of evolution
The Basic Principles of Darwinism	Chargaff's law of species specificity of DNA
Nucleic acids	1. The law of relative stability of the number of chromosomes
Cell division (meiosis) (3 laws can be included here)	2. The law of formation of morphologically similar (homologous) pairs of chromosomes of each species 3. The law of individuality of chromosomes
Metabolism and energy conversion in the biosphere	VI Vernadsky's law of biogenic migration of atoms

We come to the conclusion that the organization of the teaching of laws, theories and hypotheses in biology courses should be adapted to the level of modern biological science, new training, methods, techniques and tools. (7, p. 119).

There is a need to make changes in the teacher-student, teacher-student approach in the teaching of biological theory, law and concepts.

There are many points to consider:

- The principle of ownership of teaching in teachers;
- Bringing the interests, initiatives and desires of the learner to the forefront;
- Prevention of globalization in education;
- Creating a different educational format;
- Motivation in the learning process, ensuring the interests of both parties;
- Teacher-student synthesis;
- Organization of education, school in accordance with the requirements of the time;
- Exchange of ideas, joint activities, etc.

In order to reach the desired level of education, it is important for students to develop the following skills: logical, critical approach to new knowledge, imagination, creative application, different teaching formats, listening, communication, analysis, analysis-synthesis, the ability to ask thoughtful questions, etc. All these will ensure the use of innovations in education and, consequently, in society. What should we change in education? - To create and encourage learners' independence and freedom, to give them time. To take the questions of the young generation seriously, to conduct research together, to make them understand the responsibility of the future. What should education be like in the new era? - By developing skills. Young people can enter a new era by improving their fundamental skills. Specialized education is already considered backward in the world. We must evaluate learners with an individual approach and observation. In other words, in this century, the abilities of the human heart and soul must be emphasized, empathy must be established, and the thoughts of the future must be taken into account.

What should teachers do to change the world? - Attention should be paid to the fact that the information is lively, the learners are creative, the importance of the subjects taught should be paid; special attention should be paid to the richness of the worldview and creative work. Especially in recent years, isolation has had a negative impact on the quality of work. In this regard, it would be beneficial for societies and states to take an interest in the problems of teachers and to take care of improving their living conditions. What should a new school model look like in the new world? - Students' creativity, work done should be evaluated; Creative application of knowledge; Teachers must work collectively. This would have a motivating effect, as well as increase the tendency to creativity and research.

What is accountability in education? - Demonstration of the most exemplary works of students, assessment of the impact of artificial intelligence on education will have a greater impact on personal development. The necessity to apply technology dictates increasing attention to this area. The development of society between countries, states and enterprises must be evaluated. To understand how the world has changed; To clarify learning together, to create conditions, to be ready to change. Improving the young generation, preparing them for the new world, directing them to a different format (11, 12).

What are the factors that make technology necessary in the teaching of biology? Computer technology plays an invaluable role in showing some objects and events that cannot be observed for various reasons. For example:

- ✓ *if they are not large (nucleus structure)*
- ✓ *if it is fast-transmitting (the process of transmitting nerve impulses from neuron to neuron)*
- ✓ *if observation is not possible (embryo development)*
- ✓ *if it is difficult to explain, or rather to understand (protein synthesis)*
- ✓ *if it is not possible to demonstrate (deep water animals, alpine meadows), etc.*

In general, when organizing teaching in educational institutions with the use of modern teaching, methods and techniques, it is important to take into account an important principle: from elementary to advanced, from simple to complex, to take into account the age and level of knowledge of the class, audience. At the same time, the important task facing today's educational institutions is: to form a creative, innovative

learning and teaching potential that has mastered the modern technology and software.

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